

Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition Programs: A Tool for Economic Development

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 01, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: July 04, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Entrepreneurship, Gender, Skill Acquisition, Economic Development, Empowerment</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8111551</p>	<p><i>Entrepreneurship skills acquisition has gained unprecedented importance because of its role in economic development. This study examined the influence of skill acquisition programs as a tool for economic growth in Nigeria. The study made use of two objectives which seek to find out the influence of skill acquisition on economic development and also investigate gender differences in skill acquisition on economic development. Two hypotheses were formulated, which were drawn from the objective of the study. A survey research design was adopted in the study. The population were unemployed youths in Ondo state, Nigeria. A sample size of two hundred (200) unemployed youths was selected. A simple random sampling technique was used to select the participants. A primary source of data collection was adopted, which involved the use of a self-constructed questionnaire. Results revealed that skill acquisition has a significant influence on economic development [$F(1, 198) = 194.24$]; there is a significant gender difference in skill acquisition on economic development [$t(198) = .891, p = 0.05$] such that male youth ($M = 58.44; SD = 8.70$) have the same level of skill acquisition compared to female youths ($M = 41.56; SD = 7.52$). It was concluded that skill acquisition programmes provided for unemployed youths have actually influenced the economic development of Nigeria. It was recommended that the government should ensure that skill acquisition centres are well equipped so as to ensure a suitable learning environment; and the government should help finance those who have undergone skill acquisition programs to enable them to set up a business to become entrepreneurs.</i></p>

Introduction

The significance of skills acquisition in the societal economic development has attained a level of prominence like never before. Economically, skill acquisition stimulates markets and works effectively to create small and medium-sized businesses that offer unemployed graduates and youths alternative employment alternatives. Socially, acquiring new skills empowers people, spurs innovation, and modifies attitudes (United Nations, 2010). According to the Federal Government of Nigeria (2004), acquiring skills helps entrepreneurs become adaptable to changing circumstances by encouraging self-reliance, which reduces the problem of unemployment and promotes economic development.

Unemployment has become a major issue in most developing nations (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022). In Nigeria, most youth are unemployed. According to Federal Ministry of Labour and Productivity Report (2018), most of the unemployed youth are university graduates. As a result of unemployment, most of the youth have turned to criminal activities for survival. Few have been able to flee the country in search of greener pasture. Hassan (2013) avers that departure of youth in the country contributes to human capital resources depleting. The inability to secure a white-collar job has led to alternative means of self-employment; whereby, individual graduates have to opt for small businesses as an alternative career option as entrepreneurs.

Small businesses have for long been recognized as engines of economic growth and industrialization (Adanlawo, Reddy & Rugbeer, 2021). Accordingly, evidence is replete from developed countries and developing countries that skills acquisition contributes to the development of any country through small and medium-scale enterprises. Besides, in developing countries of Africa, where the rate of population growth oversteps employment growth, the promotion of skills acquisition is both a desirable tool for employment creation and a strategy for poverty alleviation (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2021a). Consequently, given the widespread acceptance of the role of skills acquisition as an engine of growth, several developing countries pay increasing attention to private sector development (Chinonye et al., 2015).

For any nation's economy to be developed, youth' involvement is of paramount importance. It is interesting that graduates of tertiary institutions in Nigeria today increasingly recognize that finding a white-collar job. in the present economic condition is challenging. Salihu (2014) asserts that permanent and stable are no longer

common features of career paths. As the case is now, to developing youth, especially, graduates to have the drive towards entrepreneurship skills acquisition and small business start-up, would require rebuilding them in becoming successful, independent, employers of labour and, therefore, contribute to the economy.

Skill acquisition can be defined as the form of training that can lead to the acquisition of knowledge for an individual's self-sustenance (Brand et al., 2020). It involves the training of people in different fields of trade under a legal agreement between the trainers and the trainees for a certain duration and under certain conditions. We assert that for skill to be acquired, appropriate knowledge, attitudes, habits of thought, and qualities of character are to be learnt to enable the acquirers to develop intellectual, emotional, and moral character that will prepare them for a brighter future.

Objectives of the Study

The study seeks to examine the influence of entrepreneurship skill acquisition programs on economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study is to;

- i. Find out the influence of skill acquisition on economic development
- ii. To determine the influence of gender on skill acquisition for economic development,

Hypotheses

- i. Skill acquisition has significant influence on economic development
- ii. Gender has no significant influence on skill acquisition for economic development

The Concept of Skills Acquisition

The word "skill" can have a variety of definitions depending on one's believe. According to Adeniyi (2022), a skill is an organized sequence of activities, mastery accomplished and typically presented in a flexible but systematic temporal pattern. It also includes expertise, practical ability, dexterity, and tact. The author also defined skill as the ability to perform an action repeatedly with dexterity. Therefore, a skill is a behaviour pattern that has been practiced through time. It entails acquiring performance capability. To possess a skill, is to prove the habit of acting, thinking, and behaving until a process becomes natural to the person through practice.

Adanlawo & Chaka (2022a) aver that one is said to be skilled when a procedure is completed flawlessly, effectively, and with an eye toward results. Adeniyi (2022) defined skill as the habit of acting, thinking, and behaving in a certain task in a way that the process becomes second nature to the person through repetition or practice. Skill development is important for utilizing a country's natural resources, and educational institutions, especially higher institutions, play a vital role in this process (Adanlawo, Vezi-Magigaba & Owolabi, 2021).

Omidiji & Ogwu (2019) categories skills in any training program into technical skills, human skills, and conceptual skills. The authors claim that technical abilities require knowledge of and competence in a particular activity, particularly one that involves methods, processes, procedures, or techniques. Human skills are an individual's capacity to function well in a group setting in order to promote teamwork within the group which he leads. Understanding the interconnection of an organization's multiple functions is the third one which is a conceptual skill.

Idris & Mbudai (2017) recommend using technical skills in Nigerian schools to empower or prepare young people for the workforce. There is little doubt that learning about entrepreneurship education provides opportunity for students to develop the information and attitudes necessary to take constructive actions, to create, and to become entrepreneurs. Since it is widely believed that gaining the essential skills increases a country's productive potential, Nigerian society is conscious of the need to prepare every citizen to make an effective contribution to the welfare of the nation. Additionally, it has been noted that the greatest welfare is only attained when each person contributes to the fullest extent of their abilities (Idris & Mbudai, 2017; Omidiji & Ogwu, 2018).

According to Kabir & Jazuli (2017), developing new skills is one of the most reliable ways for graduates (youths) to enter the workforce. Omidiji & Ogwu (2019) assert that skills acquisition will lead to an increase in the industrious power of a nation. This indicates that a nation whose citizens are well equipped will make a meaningful contribution to the welfare of the nation. As stated by Adanlawo, Vezi-Magigaba & Owolabi (2021), acquisition of knowledge in entrepreneurship skills is important in today's modern technological society in order to cope with the complexities. Therefore, it is pivotal for an individual who opts for entrepreneurship training to possess qualities that would enable their success. Therefore, we opine that the acquisition of appropriate skills in entrepreneurship is necessary for every young person for sustainable empowerment. Unfortunately, the majority of Nigeria's graduates do not possess skills relevant for self-employment because of the poor implementation of entrepreneurship development programmes in higher education institutions (Ekong & Ekong, 2016).

Competencies acquired through entrepreneurship skills will assist an individual to cope with the speedily changing technological environments. As such, business venture preparing should be viewed as an instrument

for changing a country's resources into finished goods and services that will advance a better quality of living (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2021c).

Skill Acquisition and Economic Development

A skill acquisition program can be regarded as experience that will enable one to participate in an occupation at different levels and to be well-equipped to produce goods and services (Adofu&Ocheja, 2013). Similarly, Magaji (2015) describes skill acquisition programs as educational training which is capable of enhancing recipients' opportunities to secure jobs in various sectors of the economy or to be self-dependent by being a job creator. According to the author, skills acquisition programmes are geared towards providing the participants with transformative capabilities that will enable socio-economic development. Skills acquisition programmes designed for youths toward youth's social-economic development, as pointed out by Kabir&Jazuli (2019), will:

1. Maintain and improve the skills and competencies of youths,
2. Contribute to resolving the problem of lack of financial capability encountered by individuals in society
3. Provide youth the chance to raise their head in society and become financially independent

Gender and Economic Development

Olagbaju (2020) avers that women and men have different or comparative roles, responsibilities, and opportunities in a particular culture. The author defines gender as the socially and culturally imposed roles and values that shape how women and men relate to one another in a particular society. It is undoubtedly not about the biological or bodily differences that are typically referred to as "sex." The economic contribution of certain sex groups is important to note. For a nation to develop economically, development policies should focus on gender equality (Adanlawo & Chaka, 2022b). The development of the economy is aided by gender equality (Manda &Mwakubo, 2014). We can therefore conclude that gender concerns are crucial to economic development policies. Therefore, every nation should endeavor to empower men and women in order to develop economically.

Empowerment

Empowerment, according to Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba (2021b)entails providing citizens with a variety of opportunities to influence changes in their standard of living. The authors contend that citizens can be inspired through empowerment to translate their ideas into original works of art. Empowerment can also be seen as a means of exposing people to skills or training that make them productive. The goal of a skill acquisition program as a measure of empowerment, according to Ukwayi,Angioha&Ojong-Ejoh (2017), is to prepare and equip individuals with appropriate skills that can be useful to them in the future. This indicates that developing the right skills might help youths reorient their values and become creators of wealth and employment rather than consumers. In essence, employment creation will reduce poverty and improved standard of living (Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba, 2022).

In line with the above view, Adanlawo & Vezi-Magigaba (2022) aver that wealth creation through empowerment is intended to address the structural weaknesses and imbalances in the economy by giving youths a strategic focus and direction. Likewise, through empowerment, virtues such as right ethics, discipline, values, hard work, honesty, respect, and humility can be inculcated in the youth. The government launched a variety of skill acquisition initiatives to help young people develop the habit of acting via repetition and practice in order to address the unemployment issue. According to Okey-Orji &Ekenedo (2019), the skill acquisition programs established in Nigeria over time consist:

- 1976Green Revolution Programme
- 1978 School-to-Land Programme
- 1986 youth employment and vocational skill development scheme of (NDE)
- 1988 small-scale industrial and graduate farmers programme of NDE
- 1988 national open apprenticeship scheme.

Different programs by succeeding governments were initiatedfor the survival of the people who are ready to work through self-reliance programmes. The government's attempts to empower the youth initially focused on agricultural output, but as time went on, the concept was diversified to include agricultural, industrial, and handcraft production that could generate. It is worth noting that different training programs have been established by the Federal and State governments to instill in the youth a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship in recent years in order to attain the intended result. The question that should come to mind is "what are the impacts of these programs on economic development?"

Research Methodology

Research Design

The researcher adopted the survey research design. The purpose of using this research design is to establish the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variables and the level of influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The population of the study are unemployed youths in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Population of the Study

The population for the study is 64,4357 unemployed youth who have undergone skill acquisition training in Ondo state.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Yamane formula is used to determine the sample size of this study. According to Yamane (2006), the formula is appropriate for a study with known population. This is shown as follows:

$$SS = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where N = population size
 e= margin error
 e= Margin of Error = 5% (0.05)

$$N=64,4357$$

$$S= \frac{64,4357}{1+64,4357(0.05)^2}$$

$$= \frac{64,4357}{1+322128.5}$$

$$S= \frac{64,4357}{322128.5}$$

$$S=199.875$$

$$S=200$$

The sampling technique process is presented above. From the above result, the sample size is 200 hundred (200) from the population of the study among unemployed youths who have undergone skill acquisition programs.

Source of Data

The source of data is primary source of data collection, which involves the use of questionnaires to obtain information from the participants in the study.

Data Analysis Techniques

The collected data were analyzed with inferential statistics such as simple regression, descriptive and ANOVA was used to analyze hypotheses 1 and 2 respectively at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: Skill acquisition has significant influence on economic development

Table 1a: Summary of Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.715a	.445	.441	5.16692

a. Predictors: (Constant), skill acquisition

Table 1a indicated that R= 0.715 which implies that there was a significant influence between the independent and the dependent variables. The R Square value of .445 indicated 4.45% of observed variance of skill acquisition on economic development.

Table 1b: Summary of Regression showing significance influence of technological usage on customer service

Model	Sum Squares	of	Mean Square	F-Cal	F-Cri	Sig.

1	Regression	3372.531	1	3372.531	194.244	3.27	0.05
	Residual	1701.509	198	17.362			
	Total	5074.040	199				

a. Predictors: (Constant), skill acquisition

b. Dependent Variable: economic development

From table 1b, skill acquisition has a significant influence on economic development [F (1, 198) 194.24]. This implies that skill acquisition is a determinant of economic development because the acquired skills would help unemployed youth develop themselves and become self-employed, allowing them to start a business.

Hypothesis 2: Gender has no significant effect of skill acquisition on economic development

Table 2a: descriptive statistics showing gender has no significant effect of skill acquisition on economic development

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper bound		
Male	100	59.0600	9.18367	.91837	57.2378	60.8822	42.00	79.00
Female	100	57.4000	8.39071	.83907	55.7351	59.0649	36.00	77.00
Total	200	59.0000	8.22347	8.22347	58.0657	59.9343	36.00	79.00

From the table above, gender, male (M = 59.06; SD = 9.18), female (M = 57.40; SD = 8.39), have the same level of skill acquisition.

Table 2b: ANOVA showing gender has no significant effect of skill acquisition on economic development

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Cal	F-Cri	P
Between Groups	493.520	2	246.760	3.715	3.34	<0.05
Within Groups	19726.480	198	66.419			
Total	2022.000	199				

From the above table, gender has significant effect of skill acquisition on economic development [f (2, 198) = 3.715; p<0.05]. This implies that male who have undergone skill acquisition tends to be more effective compare to their female counterpart.

Conclusion

Skill acquisition programmes for unemployed youths have actually influenced the economic development of Nigeria. Most of the beneficiaries are now self-employed as they practice the different skills they acquired through the acquisition programme. They are better informed about how to save money from their various vocations, grow their own businesses, and contribute to the nation's economic development.

Recommendation

1. A skills acquisition programme intended to promote economic growth should be a comprehensive initiative that gives unemployed youths the tools for a sustainable life as well as the confidence to strive for greater self-improvement.
2. Orientation programs should be organized to discourage youths from engaging in violent behavior in society and to educate them about small-scale business.
3. The government should ensure that skill acquisition centres are well equipped so as to ensure a suitable and conducive learning environment.
4. The government should assist those who have acquired entrepreneurship skills financially.

Implication

This study has the following implications:

The results of this study confirm the results of previous studies that skills acquisition and gender are important variables affecting employment creation and economic development. Citizens perceive skills acquisition programmes to have a positive effect on employment creation. Likewise, we showed that gender equality is to be considered in skills acquisition training. Both men and women possess the potential to make an equal contribution to economic development. In general, involvement of both genders in skills acquisition programs will go a long way in improving the nation's economic development.

Limitations and Future Research

This study's purpose was to investigate the influence of entrepreneurship skill acquisition programs on economic growth by conducting research using quantitative techniques. However, the following limitations are pertaining to the study. First, in this study, economic growth was used as a dependent variable for skills acquisition programs. In the future, it will be necessary to analyze the actual effects of entrepreneurship skills acquisition by looking at their effects on business sustainability. Consequently, we need to expand our research on the benefits of entrepreneurship skills acquisition programs on business management. Finally, this study limited the subjects to unemployed youths. In future studies, it is necessary to generalize the study results by considering the general public in measuring entrepreneurship skill acquisition programs' involvement.

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